

Study of the Impact and Compression After Impact behavior of Double-Double Laminate

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Abstract

This study deals with the low velocity impact and post-impact behavior of Double-Double laminates. Impact on composite structures is one of the most common and critical sources of damage. The brittleness of composite materials makes them more vulnerable to such type of loading (matrix cracking, fibre breakage, delamination). The recent Double-Double method developed by S.Tsai [1] offers new perspectives for design optimization and manufacturing. Double-Double method seems to allow a better freedom and a possible better optimization in a laminate choice. The work presented aims to understand and quantify the key damage mechanisms in these structures, as well as to compare impact and post impact response to traditional laminates, with a view to a potential replacement and weight saving. For this, drop-weight impact tests and compression after impact tests have been carried out.

Keywords: Low velocity impact, Compression after impact, Double-Double laminates, damage tolerance

1. Introduction

Impact is one of the most common and most penalizing sources of damage for composite structures. Indeed, the brittleness, heterogeneity and lamination make them more vulnerable to this effect. Impact have to be studied for laminate structures especially in the field of aeronautics as it can be critical: bird collision, hail, tool falls during maintenance [2].

The impact damages commonly observed are intralaminar matrix cracks, delaminations and fibers breakage [3,4]. The mechanisms that control the initiation and propagation of these damages are strongly influenced by the architecture of the composites. The first damage that appears is matrix cracking, then

delamination is initiated which are very penalizing for the compressive strength of the laminates [5,6].

As failure mechanisms are difficult to represent with simple models, in industry, conservative empirical models and charts have been implemented.

The Double-Double method developed by Stephen W. Tsai [1] & al. is an innovative concept of lamination. It consists of a stack of structures called “building blocks” comprising 4 angles $[\pm\varphi/\pm\psi]$ [1], [7], [8]. These angles are defined according to the desired mechanical properties and can be between 0° and 90° .

Figure 1 General principle of double-double method [12]

This method was developed to provide more freedom in the sizing and to bypass the restrictive lamination rules for manufacturers. Better optimization for composite seems possible.

Double-Double laminates are different than traditional ones (interface numbers, mismatch angle, homogenization...). Because of these properties, impact and compression after impact behavior may be different from traditional laminate behavior and challenge the principles of impact sizing.

There are a few studies that focus on the impact tolerance of Double-Double composites [9],[10],[11].

The research is still in its early stages, and no study has reached a definitive conclusion. A deeper understanding of the damage mechanisms in this type of laminate is needed.

The objective of this paper is to compare the response to low-velocity impact and post-impact of a Double-Double laminate and a traditional laminate. To do so, a traditional oriented laminate was chosen as the basis of

the study named QUAD in this paper, the chosen Double-Double laminate has the same elastic properties in the plane and similar flexural properties as the reference laminate. So, the differences in stratification of the Double-Double method (angle between 0 and 90, homogenization, inter-ply angle, numbers of interface, etc...) compared to the traditional method are really studied. These two configurations were tested under low-speed impact for energies of 9J, 16J and 25J. Some specimens were analyzed using Tomography. Finally, these two configurations were tested under compression (Compression After Impact) in order to fully evaluate the impact tolerances of these two configurations. The tests were carried out according to ASTM D7136/D7136M and ASTM D7137/7137M standards.

2. Material and Methodology

2.1. Material and Stacking sequence design.

In this work, the material used was Toray 2510 Prepreg, P707AG-15 Fiber T700G. The

unidirectional propriety are summarized in Table 1. The base line Quad laminate was selected not according to the ASTM D7136. The QUAD stacking sequence is [45/0₂/-45/90₂/45/0₃/-45/90], resulting of a total thickness of 3.65 mm.

The configuration of the Double-Double laminate was made so that the in plane and flexion elastic properties are nearly the same as the QUAD laminate properties. For the comparison study it is important to have the same membrane stiffness for in plane load, whereas in impact test bending stiffness is more relevant.

The classic laminate theory (CLT) describes the behavior of laminate with the matrix [A, B, D] :

$$\begin{bmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{bmatrix}$$

With;

A: in-plane stiffness matrix

B: membrane-bending coupling matrix

D: Bending stiffness matrix

It was arbitrary decided to have a perfect match for the in-plan properties and nearly the same for bending properties.

A way to achieve that is to use the laminates parameters. Tsai and Pagano [13] demonstrate that matrix A, B and D are a combination of materials parameters and laminates parameters. These lamination parameters depend only on the stacking sequence of the laminate (orientation and positioning of the plies)

In-plane laminates parameters $\xi_{A,Quad}^1, \xi_{A,Quad}^2$ were evaluated for the QUAD laminate and the angles of Double-Double were calculated with this:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Quad stacking sequence} &\longrightarrow (\xi_{A,Quad}^1, \xi_{A,Quad}^2) \\ (\xi_{A,Quad}^1, \xi_{A,Quad}^2) &\longrightarrow (\xi_{A,DD}^1, \xi_{A,DD}^2) \\ (\xi_{A,DD}^1, \xi_{A,DD}^2) &\longrightarrow \varphi \text{ and } \psi \end{aligned}$$

The Double-Double laminate for this specimen based on the extensional stiffness matrix was [7/-64/64/-7]_{6T}. For these specimens, a perfect match was achieved with the [A] matrix and [D] matrix were quite similar. The A, B and D matrix are summarized in table 2.

Concerning the bending stiffness, the difference between the maximum of the matrix coefficient D_{11} is less than 2%. Moreover, according to Christoforou [14] the response of FRP under low velocity impact is a function of the equivalent bending stiffness $D_{eq} = \sqrt{\frac{A+1}{2} D_{11} D_{22}}$, where $A = \frac{D_{12}+2D_{16}}{\sqrt{D_{11}D_{22}}}$. The difference in equivalent bending stiffness between the laminates is less than 3%. It can be considered that Double-Double and Quad specimen have nearly the same elastics properties.

Engineering constant	Identification
E_1	[GPa] 125
E_2	[GPa] 8.41
ν_{12}	- 0.31
G_{12}	[GPa] 4.23
ρ	[kg.m ⁻³] 1 517
Ply thickness	[mm] 0.152

Table 1 Materials properties

The absence of mirror symmetry does not allow to obtain a zero-coupling matrix B. Mechanical couplings and thermal warping may exist. Homogenization makes it possible to overcome these problems. The repetition of building block makes it possible to obtain a "homogeneous" distribution of plies in the thickness of the laminate. Homogenization allows Double-Double laminates to behave like a homogeneous orthotropic material — meaning no mechanical coupling, no thermal

Matrix A, B and D for the Quad laminate:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 247 & 43.7 & 0 \\ 43.7 & 175 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 49.5 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^6 \quad D = \begin{bmatrix} 283 & 57.3 & 18.1 \\ 57.3 & 167 & 18.1 \\ 18.1 & 18.1 & 63.8 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and } B = [0]_{3,3}$$

Matrix A, B and D for the Double-Double laminate:

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 247 & 43.7 & 0 \\ 43.7 & 175 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 49.5 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^6 \quad D = \begin{bmatrix} 278 & 47.8 & 0 \\ 47.8 & 191 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 54.3 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and } B = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & -4820 \\ 0 & 0 & 4820 \\ -4820 & 4810 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Table 2 Matrix A (Pa.m), B (Pa.m²) and D (Pa.m³)

warping. While perfect homogenization is never truly achieved, increasing the repetition of building block brings the laminate closer to this ideal behavior. For this reason, a homogenization criterion has been defined [1]. When this criterion is met, the laminate is generally expected to exhibit no warping during curing, no excessive residual stresses, and no membrane-flexural coupling.

Homogenization criterion [1]:

$$|A^* - D^*| < 2\% Tsai$$

and

$$|B^*| < 2\% Tsai$$

With $A^* = \frac{A}{h}$; $B^* = \frac{2B}{h^2}$; $D^* = \frac{12D}{h^3}$ and

h the laminate thickness

The criterion is validated by the Double-Double laminate.

The two laminates therefore exhibit similar macroscopic elastic behavior in theory. However, from a mesoscopic perspective, the ply orientations differ between them, leading to a different distribution of both in-plane and out-of-plane stresses. Additionally, the number of interfaces and the inter-ply angles vary between the two stacking sequences.

Specimen	Quad	Double-Double
Number of interface	14	23
Inter-angle ply	Always 45°	Variable 72°, 53° et 14°

Table 3 Laminates configurations

2.2. Drop-weight and compression after impacts test

2.2.1. Drop-weight

Specimen were tested for low-velocity impact using a drop-weight device with a mass of 2 kg and an hemispheric impactor with a diameter of 16 mm for impact speeds between 3 and 5 m/s. The specimen dimensions are 150 x 100 mm. These low-velocity impacts are characteristic of so-called "classic" incidents in the workshop, such as tools falling onto parts or collisions during transport. The specimens were placed over a flat support fixture base with a 125 x 75 mm rectangular frame, which allowed the impactor to contact through the specimen without interferences.

Figure 2 Impact test setup

Impact energies of 9 J, 16 J, and 25 J were applied, corresponding respectively to impact velocities of 3 m/s, 4 m/s, and 5 m/s. For each energy level, two specimens per configuration were tested.

2.2.2. Compression after impact test

The Compression After Impact (CAI) tests were performed using a Hydraulic test machine (Schenk PCS 450 kN) and a 250 kN load cell. To prevent global buckling, anti-buckling devices were implemented. Digital image correlation was employed to identify the buckling mode and monitor strain evolution.

Figure 3 CAI test apparatus

3. Results

At 3 m/s, the damage induced is not significant enough to observe clear differences in either the impact response or the compression after impact performance. For the highest speed (5m/s), the samples are fully perforated so the difference in behavior between QUAD and Double-Double laminate is not relevant.

Fig 4 shows a comparison between the response of the two stacking sequences at $4 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ ($E = 16\text{J}$). It can first be observed that both laminates exhibit similar elastic behavior, which confirms the relevance of the selected stacking sequence. However, the energy dissipated by the Quad laminates is significantly higher than that dissipated by the Double-Double laminates. The first noticeable drop in stiffness — indicative of the onset of severe damage — does not occur at the same load level. The Quad laminates show a gradual reduction in stiffness starting around 3 kN, whereas the Double-Double laminates experience a more abrupt drop later, at approximately 3.8 kN, suggesting a delayed but more sudden damage initiation.

To complete this study, X-ray computed tomography (CT) scans were performed. Figure 5 shows the total delaminated area for both stacking configurations. The Quad laminates exhibit approximately twice the delaminated area ($15\,400 \text{ mm}^2$) compared to the Double-Double laminates (8000 mm^2), suggesting that the Quad laminates sustained more severe damage during impact.

The delamination shape in the Quad laminates corresponds to the typical patterns observed in this type of test. In contrast, the Double-Double laminates display more circular delamination zones, likely due to their distinct $\pm 45^\circ$ inter-ply angles. Interestingly, while the Double-Double laminates present a greater number of delaminated interfaces, these are smaller in size. Conversely, the Quad laminates exhibit fewer delaminated interfaces, but the damage is more severe at each one.

This suggests that the Double-Double stacking sequence may distribute impact energy more effectively across multiple interfaces, leading to smaller, more controlled delaminations.

Figure 6 presents the results of the compression-after-impact (CAI) tests. As expected, both laminates exhibit similar elastic behavior. However, the failure load is significantly higher for the Double-Double laminates, reaching 50 kN compared to 33 kN for the Quad laminates. This corresponds to failure stresses of 137 MPa and 90 MPa, respectively. This difference in residual strength can be attributed to the extensive delamination observed in the Quad laminates. The large delaminated areas result in the formation of several thinner sub-laminates, which are more prone to local buckling and thus offer lower post-impact compressive resistance.

Additionally, the failure modes differ notably: the Double-Double laminates exhibit a more abrupt, brittle failure, whereas the Quad laminates show a more progressive failure behavior.

Figure 4 Impact results at 4 m/s for Quad & Double-Double laminates

Figure 5 Delaminated surfaces after impact at 4 m/s on a Double-Double laminate (left) & Quad (right)

Figure 6 CAI results with LVI at 4 m/s for Quad & Double-Double laminate

4. Conclusion & perspectives

In this study, the response of a Double-Double laminate was analyzed and compared to that of a traditional Quad laminate with equivalent elastic properties. The selected Double-Double configuration appears to exhibit better damage tolerance than its Quad counterpart. However, caution is warranted: only one Double-Double configuration was studied, and the Quad laminate used for comparison may not have had the most optimized ply dispersion, as the primary objective was to comply with all the traditional design constraints.

Beyond the number of interfaces, other factors may contribute to the improved performance of the Double-Double laminate—such as a more favorable distribution of transverse shear stresses, the absence of bending-twisting coupling, or differing interfacial properties. Further investigation is necessary to better understand the damage mechanisms involved. Digital image correlation will be used to analyze both global and local buckling behavior of the specimens.

Since Double-Double laminates represent a broad class of layups, no general conclusions can be drawn based on the study of a single configuration. Future work will involve exploring other Double-Double configurations with varied angles and stacking sequences.

In addition to impact and compression-after-impact tests, quasi-static tests will be conducted to further understand the damage evolution in this type of laminate. To complement the experimental work, a numerical campaign will be carried out using the semi-continuous model developed at the Clément Ader Institute of Toulouse [15].

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